

EVALUATING OF CITIZEN INVOLVEMENT IN THE LANDSCAPE ENVIRONMENT OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF ALGIERS-CENTER (ALGERIA)

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Abstract

Exploring the Chi-square tests, the current paper attempts to assess the impact of the gender and the age of gardens visitors on their interest to be involved in the environmental improvement. The study is based on quantitative approach, the two face-to-face surveys, conducted in May 2021 and September 15-30, 2022, among 37 and 192 participants respectively in Khemisti gardens in the capital of Algeria. Consequently, the results indicated that the dependence between the selected variables isn't confirmed. ($P > 0.05$).

Keywords: Algiers-Center, Urban Planning, Citizen Participation, Algeria, Chi-square Tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

Citizen participation is considered a tool to support local management and governance, insofar as it provides the lessons necessary to understand the use and expectations of citizens. This tool saves time as well as successful implementation of urban landscape projects, provided that you choose the right method of approaching the social sample concerned to inform them, convince them and communicate with related projects data. Hence, the choice of approach method therefore varies depending on the scale and type of project to be carried out. Indeed, there are several studies interested in urban planning (Montembault, & Geisler, 2016; Messaoudene, & Messaoudi, 2016; Merzelkad-Hallal, & Merzelkad-Nedjai, 2024; Makhloufi, 2010; Kiss, et al 2022; Hurard, 2011; Bariol-Mathais, 2017; Boumediene, 2013).

Since the beginning of the 1990s, Algeria has been committed to protocols relating to sustainable development and is committed to practicing good governance in terms of territorial planning. The country has undergone institutional reforms in recent years, and more particularly the introduction in the 2016 constitution of participatory democracy at the level of local authorities. In this context, participatory actions refer to the role of associations and their participation in the development process, as well as to the

encouragement of local communities to participatory democracy through civil society (Ministry of the Interior, Communities local authorities and regional planning, 2024).

Some studies suggested that the participatory approach in the management of Algerian cities follows top-down logic and is often limited to a simple formality, rather than a true shared management approach (Messaoudene & Messaoudi, 2016).

This article aims to question the use of the concept of citizen participation in the field of town planning and urban policies. Our intention is to try to assess citizens' perceptions of this approach. To this end, we propose an exploratory study on a sample of the population of the municipality of Algiers-Center and their apprehensions in relation to development or redevelopment operations of public spaces: "Public space is not only feasible data, it is constructed by the practices and representations of individuals" (Makhloufi, 2010). This study is about the city of Algiers-Center and its gardens. The gardens were renovated in the last ten years as part of the city's plan to grow by 2030.

The choice fell on two samples, one non-probabilistic accidental with blind sorting of the inhabitants of three districts of the commune of Algiers-Center, and the other non-probabilistic with sorting oriented for users of a public space in the commune: Khemisti garden. Hence, the current paper take place in three stages: we will first focus on the notion of citizen participation to appreciate its meaning. Secondly, we will offer a summary assessment of the Algerian experience in terms of commitment to the establishment of a citizen participation policy. Thirdly, the results of field surveys will be presented in order to discuss the degree of citizen involvement in projects on public spaces.

1.1. Modalities for citizen participation

It is important to mention that the participation of citizens in the urban projects of their municipality must be done according to studied mechanisms. According to research in this area, we can evoke a first modality which expresses the meaning of participatory commitment, does it come from political decision-makers or from citizens? In the first case, we are talking about top-down participation with its English name called Top Down which means from top to bottom. In the second case, we will talk about bottom-up participation, which this time means from bottom to top (Hurard, 2011).

In the first modality, reasoning follows a traditional conception of power, which comes from above with orders or decisions to be applied rigidly, without taking into consideration the realities on the ground (Géoconfluences, 2020). Public authorities have a duty in this case to inform citizens, consult them by inviting them to consultation sessions or workshops, or at least verify their opinions through a survey or opinion poll. Also, invite them to co-construction, or co-management of the project. The limits that this mode of participation could have are that:

- The elected official is free to follow or not follow the opinion of citizens.
- Participation can only be formal.
- Participation can sometimes be difficult to obtain due to lack of interest on the part of stakeholders, or difficulties in accessing them.

In the second modality, ideas and wishes emanate from society, to be transmitted to the authorities, the latter only playing the role of transmission between the parties. However, this approach can take the form of a demand only through demonstrations or gatherings, especially if it is present in countries where the population is suspicious of the authorities, and where there is an absence of institutionalization of participation. (Hurard, 2011).

According to our thinking, there is another typology of citizen participation which is related this time to the temporality of commitment. Indeed, in an urban project, there are generally three stages:

- Ideation of the design: in this study phase, the municipality or other territorial body should launch an opinion poll campaign by any means of communication (on the internet for example), to consult the opinions of project users on their expectations and needs.
- Construction and works: in this construction and monitoring phase, citizens are invited to participate manually in light work of course (finishing, planting, and decorations for example), under the supervision of an expert (architect, designer or landscaper).
- Delivery and use of the project: in this management phase, users participate in the maintenance and proper functioning of the project. This can be done financially (an annual tax for example).

1.2. Citizen participation and Algerian legislation

The procedures for preparing the two main urban planning instruments in Algeria, namely the PDAU (Master Plan for Development and Urban Planning) and the POS (Land Use Plan), provide for the presence of representatives of the company civil, at least in the form of professional associations, but there is no practical implementation of decisions that would consider participation (Boumedienne, 2013).

These two instruments come from law 90-29 of December 1, 1990 relating to development and town planning defining the general rules for town planning and construction.

The public inquiries for the latter two do not carry major expressions and are seen rather as sources of conflict on the part of local authorities. In this context, a cooperation project was initiated with the United Nations development program supported by the European Union which aims to promote the involvement of citizens and civil society in municipal management and sustainable local development.

This program entitled CapDeL (Capacity Building Program for Local Development Actors) is based on the development of municipal charters of citizen participation which organize dialogue, planning and management bodies, concerted with local stakeholders, through municipal advisory councils. From this perspective, Communal Development Plans (PCD) will emerge.

According to the report published and posted online by the project management unit of the CapDeL program in 2017, the PCD's participatory approach brings advantages such as:

- Improve understanding of local issues and their interrelationships through increased information sharing.
- Integrate multiple points of view and ideas resulting in improved solutions and actions.
- Strengthen among participants the feeling of belonging to the community.
- Promote accountability for projects and ownership of initiatives by various local stakeholders.

Ten pilot municipalities were chosen to start the operation throughout the country. Local elected officials developed three types of workshops: Participatory democracy, Administrative, technical and social services, and lastly, economic and local development. As we emphasized above, citizen participation cannot be achieved without prior information and communication work. Inform to understand and be able to contribute subsequently (Bariol-Mathais, 2017). Hence, one of the major conclusions of the first workshop included in the CapDeL program on participatory democracy is that access for all citizens to all relevant information concerning their municipality and local management should be systematized and permanently ensured. Indeed, "information is the prerequisite for participatory democracy", it constitutes the first step that must be taken by elected officials and by local administration (CapDeL Report, 2017).

Moreover, the CapDeL report specified that: "information to citizens by the municipality must develop through the internet and social networks. For this, it was proposed to create a communication unit at the municipal level, and to open official municipal pages on social networks. The unit would be responsible for local information. This unit would be supervised by an elected official responsible for participatory democracy. » (CapDeL Report, 2017). In several municipalities, the creation of an interactive space on municipal websites allows citizens to share their messages and discuss about their priorities. Thus, improving access to information requires strengthening the institutional and individual capacities of local authorities, elected officials and executives in terms of communication. Furthermore, to establish a legal framework for citizen involvement, the participants suggested the creation of citizen charters, which specify the conditions of participation.

Apart from the CapDeL, there are two laws of Algerian legislation containing articles relating to citizen participation and participatory democracy. Firstly, law No. 06-06 of February 20, 2006 relating to the city's orientation law which promulgates in articles 02 and 17, recommendations concerning local management. Secondly, law No. 10-11 of 22 June 2011 relating to the municipality, which includes a third title entitled: "Citizen participation in the management of the municipality", also with recommendations and directives for informing citizens, and the implementation support aimed at getting them interested and encouraging them to participate in the affairs of their municipality. After reading the texts, we noticed that the legislation on citizen participation remains

superficial with general recommendations, however, the emphasis was placed on two essential points raised in these laws which are: local management and information. Local management therefore comes with a decentralization of decision-making powers, a detailed institutionalization of participation and a definition of the exact role of the citizen from upstream to downstream of the project (Montembault et al. 2016).

Fig 1: The multiple facets of user expertise

Source: Montembault et al. 2016. Readapted by the authors.

However, the information should it still necessary to specify the category to be informed? Should participation be open to all or targeted? How to evaluate if it is representative? How can we get this sample of the population?

Consequently, the website remains the most open tool for information and communication, with local media such as newspapers and radio possibly coming next. Posters among the Municipal People's Council reduce the level of openness, and then social networks such as groups on Facebook and Instagram on the other hand constitute a target on which the effort of soliciting participation could be concentrated. Finally, we can cite email boxes and telephone numbers which remain less easy to access, and could only be used in cases where participation concerns local actors or specialists in a very specific field, due to their skills or their activities.

Fig 2: Communication tools from the most open to the most closed

Source: Montembeault et al. 2016. Adapted by the authors.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. Hypotheses

The study investigates whether personal factors had a significant impact on the environmental attitude during and post- the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, the research hypotheses are presented below:

- H1.** Gender significantly influences the type of participation in environmental projects during Covid-19 pandemic.
- H2.** The type of participation in environmental projects is significantly affected by the age of citizens during Covid-19 epidemic.
- H3.** The age of participants impacts significantly on the preference for local gardens or urban parks.
- H4.** The age influences on expectations and needs of citizens.
- H5.** The age of participants shapes the type of participation in environmental projects after Covid-19 outbreak.
- H6.** Expectations are driven by gender of citizens
- H7.** Gender influences the type of participation in environmental projects after Covid-19 pandemic.
- H8.** Origin of respondents has an important effect on the neighborhood of gardens.

2.2. Method of Sampling

Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used in order to respond to study problem, which refers to the assessment of citizen involvement in operations on public spaces in Algiers-Center. Thus, two surveys were carried out in 2021 and 2022, with face to face questionnaires among citizens, and semi-directive interviews with those who are responsible for urban planning.

Initially, a questionnaire was intended for users of the two Khemisti gardens located on the street of the same name (Khemisti Street), in May 2021. The aim was to measure the degree of involvement of users of public gardens in the daily urban landscape in Algiers-Center. The questions related to several aspects (in addition to socio-demographic data: age, gender, profession, place of residence), we took four for our study, which are: (1) knowledge of the history of creation of the gardens, (2) the name of the gardens, (3) the redevelopment project from which the Khemisti gardens would benefit in the same year (2021), (4) the type of participation desired. In total, 37 citizens were interviewed, and it was the total number of garden visitors found on site at that time: weekday from 12 p.m. to 2 p.m.

The second questionnaire, consisting of several parts, included in a thesis work in progress, was distributed between September 15 and 30, 2022 among 192 inhabitants in the three districts surrounding the Khemisti gardens. In this article, we used two sections of questions which are personal information (socio-demographic characteristics: age,

gender, origin), the attendance and participation section with the following questions: (1) appreciation of the development and maintenance of the gardens, (2) the preference of residents for local gardens or urban parks, (3) prior knowledge or not of the redevelopment project from which the gardens benefited in 2021, (4) their expectations, (5) the type of participation desired. These questionnaires were administered with a face-to-face method. The results of these surveys are presented according to user categories: residents/visitors. Chi-square tests will be explored for the socio-demographic data (independent variables) and the other dependent variables listed above in order to comprehensively measure the degree of citizen involvement between the categories of gender, age, and origin of respondents.

Fig 3: Urban situation of Algiers-Center's gardens

Source: Authors.

To bring the university closer to local stakeholders and other socio-economic collaborators, this citizen participation project submitted to central Algiers, serving the renovation and urban development of the municipality. According to our interviews carried out at the end of February 2022, with the director Mr. Acef, the latter told us that citizen participation is welcome but on condition of respecting the conceptual aspect, and not altering the technical aspects and construction materials employees. According to him, “limiting the framework for citizen participation is essential; otherwise, consultation could lead to conflicts”.

The director also informed us of a previous experiment carried out by the municipality, in the field of participation during the year 2009, and which was entitled: “City Committee”. A meeting with members of the central Algiers neighborhood committee was held every week to assess the living conditions of citizens and propose solutions to the problems raised. Consequently, it is necessary to establish a good understanding of the projects to

be developed, in order to then be able to communicate them to citizens. Horizontal consultation is therefore recommended, on the one hand, between the different services at the Municipal People's Council level, and on the other hand, with other organizations such as the Wilaya (first degree territorial entity at the level of the Algerian territorial division) and the Ministry of Culture.

Furthermore, an Municipal People's Council ensured Local Action Plan (PAL) by establishing each year by a technical team which decides on the work to be carried out during the current year, and studies their feasibility. In the action plans, citizens' requests are submitted to the registry office and are taken into consideration. However, at present, most of the complaints received concern road reconstruction or repair work. Finally, regarding the redevelopment project for the lower part of the Khemisti garden, a panel was posted showing the perspective of the development proposal by the winning design office, two months before the start of the work.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. Descriptive statistics

This section highlights descriptive statistics to reveal the demographic characteristics of the sampled population. Overall, Due to Covid-19 pandemic, the first survey was limited to 30 participants (22 men; 15 women) 40.54 % of them were aged 18-25 years old. Moreover, it has been missed 7 responses (n=37).

Fig 4: Gender of respondents (n=37)

Source: Survey data

Fig 5: Age groups of respondents (n=37)

Source: Survey data

Additionally, the second survey included 192 participants, most of them were men (n=129; 67.2 %). Taking respondents' age into consideration, the majority of the survey sample aged 41-60 years old (n= 67; 34.9 %), followed with citizens who had 26-40 years old (n= 64; 33.3 %).

Fig 6: Gender of respondents (n=192) **Fig 7: Age groups of respondents (n=192)**

Source: Survey data

Source: Survey data

3.2. Chi-square tests

A Chi-square test (χ^2) was conducted to evaluate the association between selected personal factors (i.e. Gender, age), and some variables corresponding to environmental interest. It should be emphasized that Chi-square test is used once two qualitative variables are indicated. In this regard, it is useful to argue that gender, age cohort are qualitative factors. Thus, It should be outlined that in economic research, it is appropriate to use the term (Man/Women) to switch out the term (Male/Female) because the last one is more relevant to biological and physical aspects (Boukhedimi, 2022). According to the Chi-square test's results, there are no significant differences found regarding the current study hypotheses ($p > 0.05$), as indicated in the table 1.

Table 1: Chi-square tests & hypothesis results

Hypothesises	P-value	Result	Statistic hypotheses		Study hypotheses	Survey period
			H ₀	H ₁		
H1	0.566	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	May 2021
H2	0.942	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	
H3	0.402	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	September 15-30, 2022
H4	0.219	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	
H5	0.895	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	
H6	0.294	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	
H6	0.888	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	
H8	0.730	Independence	Accepted	Rejected	Infirmed	

Source: Survey data

Further, most of the men (62.5%) and women (35.71%) preferred to share their opinions and ideas as a tool to participate to improve gardens, the same observation was indicated in post-the Covid-19 epidemic (men: 37.98%; women: 38.1 %). In Addition to that, both security and cleanliness are the same expectations wanted by men (24.81 %) and women (22.22 %). Considering the age groups of participants, it has been determined that the

majority of each age cohort replied that sharing their opinions is the favorite manner to be involved in their natural environment during and after the Covid-19 outbreak. Thus, the age group didn't influence on the expectations and needs of visitors (Security & cleanliness). Furthermore, most of the respondents are not satisfied with the quality of visited garden. In this sense, it is standing to note that real citizens of Algiers confirmed that the targeted gardens are part of their neighborhood, on the other hand, these gardens are near to their own homes.

3.3. Contributions from experience and deduced orientations

- Experience has shown that there are several empty links in the transmission chain of a possible participatory approach. Landscaping professionals should be included in this chain with a major role in maintaining good local governance in landscape projects.
- Initiating a reflection on the real issues surrounding public squares and gardens in an urban environment involves a landscape project where the political, cultural, economic and environmental dimensions are perceived.
- Initiating a horizontal consultation between the different actors upstream of the landscape project will make it possible to not reduce these spaces to simple urban ornaments, and to limit the work to that of the image only as in 19th century town planning century.
- Electronic participation is a way to approach social identifiers, and determine their expectations, but also their contributions to landscape projects. We must therefore instill the culture of online participation in citizens from an early age.

4. CONCLUSION

The contribution of the Algerian citizen to his municipality should not be limited to a short list of demands linked to the maintenance of roads or buildings, but should integrate a system of sharing and consultation, supported by executive institutionalization. Indeed, we plead for decisions concerning public garden redevelopment projects to be concerted between the three main stakeholders: local institutions, citizens and professionals (architects, town planners and landscape gardener). This research paper therefore was meant to look at how gender and age groups affect the citizens' involvement in gardens assessment among Algerian visitors. Consequently, it has not been shown any correlation between the examined variables in this inquiry.

To conclude, it is essential to point out that the findings of the proposed article could be very relevant to the scientific research by supporting the results obtained. Thus, the final sample size of the first survey (n=30) could be considered the limit of this study, although the central limit theory (CLT) states that the sample is representative once the number is equal or superior to 30 (Chang et al, 2006; Polya, 1920; Johnson, 2004; Urdan, 2005; Berenson et al, 2012; Bajpai, 2013; Elsherif, 2021; Boukhedimi et al, 2023; Rish, 2023). In addition to that, it would be more interested to involve participants aged more than 60 years old, and women in the future research.

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